

IS THE SYSTEMIC IMMUN-INDUCTION INDEX A PROGNOSTIC FACTOR FOR ADRENAL MASSES?

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ABSTRACT Adrenal masses may sometimes carry malignant potential such as carcinomas, and sometimes carry benign potential a functional adenoma. It is quite difficult to know beforehand without histopathological examination. We compared the demanded inflammatory inflammation index (SII) used in inflammatory processes and also in recent years, in predictive efficacy research in oncological processes such as gastric cancer and pancreatic cancer, based on adrenal masses based on the results of adrenalectomy in our clinic.

KEYWORDS Adrenal mass, Adrenalectomy, Systemic immune inflammation index

Introduction

Suprarenal masses are one of the most common tumours seen in autopsy series and are seen in 3% of people over 50 years of age. While most of the adrenal masses are asymptomatic, a small proportion of them produce hormones, and a smaller proportion (1/4000) shows malignant features. [1] It is necessary to evaluate whether the mass is hormonally active, whether it is benign or malignant before the surgical intervention due to adrenal mass. This assessment is expected to reduce the complications during treatment. This indicator, based on Neutrophil (N), Platelet (P), leukocyte (L) counts, is called a systemic immune inflammation index (SII) and has been shown to be a prognostic marker for determining the behaviour of solid tumours. [2-4] This indicator can reflect the balance of the host immune and inflammatory condition in a comprehensive manner.

In our study, we investigated the efficacy of calculated systemic immune inflammation indices in the determination of the malignant potential of solid masses in patients undergoing adrenalectomy.

Materials and Method

Between December 2014 and August 2018, 66 patients who underwent adrenalectomy ranging from 23 to 73 ages were evaluated retrospectively. Postoperative pathology diagnoses and preoperative hemogram values of systemic immune inflammation indices were compared.

While creating groups; lesions such as hemangioma, lymphangioma, benign cystic formation, and adrenal hyperplasia (n13) which are rare, but shows high survival rates; and such as adrenocortical adenoma, neoplasm, oncocytic carcinoma, pheochromocytoma, neuroblastic tumor and carcinoma metastasis (n52) which are commonly seen and shows low survival rate were compared. Data of preoperative laboratory examination were taken and neutrophil, platelet and leukocyte counts were used. SII is defined as $SII = N \times T / L$ [5],[6]

MedCalc 18.11 program was used in the implementation of statistical analysis. Continuous data were given as mean $\pm$ standard deviation. Categorical data were given as a percentage (%). Shapiro Wilk test was used to investigate the suitability of the data for normal distribution. Mann-Whitney U test was used for the twice groups, and the Kruskal-Wallis H test was used for the groups with three or higher components. Pearson's chi-square analysis was used in the analysis of the cross tables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered as a criterion for statistical significance.

Findings

Of 66 patients undergoing adrenalectomy, two were bilateral (3,03%), 41 were left (62,12%), 23 (34,84%) were right adrenalectomy, and 45 were female, and 21 were male. The laparoscopic

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Table 1 Distribution of patients undergoing adrenalectomy according to gender, surgical technique and side information

Gender	Number (Percentage)
Female	45(% 68.18)
Male	21 (% 31.81)
Surgical Technique	
Open surgery	20(% 30.30)
Laparoscopic	46 (% 69.69)
Side	
Left	41(% 62.12)
Right	23(% 34.84)
Bilaterally	2 (% 3.03)

Table 2 Histopathological results.

Histopathological Results	Number (Percentage)
Adrenocortical adenomas	17 (%25)
Adrenocortical neoplasms	13 (%19,11)
Pheochromasitoma	13 (%19,11)
Bening cystic masses	6 (%8,82)
Carcinoma metastases	4 (%5,88)
Adrenocortical onc.carcinomas	4 (%5,88)
Lymphangiomas	3 (%4,41)
Adrenal hyperplasia	3 (%4,41)
Paragangliomas	2 (%2,94)
Feo.+Ganglioneuroma	1(%1,47)
A neuroblastic tumour	1(%1,47)
Cavernous hemangioma	1 (%1,47)
Total	68(%100)

operation was performed in 46 (% 69,69) of the patients. (Table 1)

Postoperative histopathological results included 17 adrenocortical adenomas (25%) 13 adrenocortical neoplasms (19,11%), 13 pheochromocytomas (19,11%), 6 benign cystic events (8,82%), 4 carcinoma metastases (5,88%), 4 adrenocortical oncocytic carcinomas (%). 5,88), 3 lymphangiomas (4,41%), 3 adrenal hyperplasia (4,41%), 2 paragangliomas (2,94%), 1 pheochromocytoma + ganglioneuroma (1,47%), 1 neuroblastic tumor (1%) , 47), 1 cavernous hemangioma (1.47%). (Table 2)

There was a significant difference in the comparison between the lesions (hemangioma, lymphangioma, benign cystic formation, and adrenal hyperplasia) that did not affect the prognosis and affect the prognosis (adrenocortical adenoma, neoplasm, oncocytic carcinoma, pheochromocytoma, neuroblastic tumour and carcinoma metastasis) with Mann-Whitney U test. (P <0.05) (Table 3)

Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test

Total N	65
Mann-Whitney U	505,000
Wilcoxon W	1.883,000
Test Statistic	505,000
Standard Error	60,973
Standardized Test Statistic	2,739
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	,006

Table.3. Mann-Whitney U test.

Discussion

94% of the masses of adrenal masses are benign, 90% are not functional, and 80% are smaller than 2 cm in diameter. The incidence of malignant adrenal gland tumours was found to be 2.7%, and its diameter was generally above 5 cm. [7] In the preoperative period, malignant potential can be differentiated from benign potential by many invasive methods. However, using a prognostic indicator analysed in blood values such as SII; may reduce cost and morbidity significantly. [8-9]

Tumour cells affect proinflammatory mediators, and systemic inflammation increases tumour cell proliferation, migration, and invasion by inhibiting apoptosis and promoting angiogenesis. Several studies have shown that systemic immune and inflammatory cells, such as neutrophils, monocytes, platelets, and lymphocytes, are associated with the prognostic value in many malignancies. [10-12] However, these predictors are usually based on one or two inflammatory cells, and the predictive ability for tumours may not be optimal. Nowadays, SII, which is based on neutrophils, platelets and lymphocyte counts and can reflect the balance of host immune and inflammatory states, has been developed as an independent predictor of the clinical outcomes of cancer in clinical practice. [13] Cancer and inflammation are closely linked, and various potential mechanisms can be used to explain that high SII is associated with survival. Tumour microenvironment, as well as tumour cells living in inflammatory cells, are very important in carcinogens and angiogenesis. [14-16]

Result

Our study shows that the presence of a high index of systemic immune inflammation in the lesions affecting the prognosis was found to be helpful in demonstrating the identity of the masses. For this reason, it is suggested that simple, inexpensive and noninvasive SII can be used to determine the identity of adrenal masses with preoperative hemogram.

The most important limiting factor of the study is that the number of patients should be higher.

We believe that this study, which we have done in clinics with a higher volume of cases, will show more positive results.

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